

EMPLOYMENT AND DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA: A STUDY IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract:

India is the world's second largest country in the world which is the youngest nation having the largest number of people in the working age group. The employment condition in the country have undergone some imperative changes in response to the hastened growth of the aggregate economy. As we look around we see the vulnerable situation of the informal sector workers represented the total insufficiency of the job security safeguard that formal sector unions are fighting for their rights. Our Indian economy had experienced leading policy changes in early 1990s. The new economic reform, popularly known as, Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization designed at building the Indian economy as fastest mounting economy and that too globally competitive. The leading features of employment and unemployment in India are a sign of those in developing countries and at hand there are little rates of unemployment but much higher levels of poverty. The globalization has brought in new infringe to developing countries. Generously proportioned way in to developed country markets and technology shift hold out assurance improved productivity and higher living standard. Globalization has also alarmed up new challenges like growing inequality across and inside nations, unsteadiness in financial market and environmental issues. Decay is unhelpful feature of globalization is that an enormous mainstream of developing countries stay behind removed from the course. Till the 90's the progression of globalization of the Indian economy was pocket watch over by the wall of trade and investment liberalization of trade, investment and financial flows initiated in the 90's has gradually lowered the barriers to competition and hastened the swiftness of globalization. Unemployment is a terrifying problem for both the developed and developing countries. India is one of those developing countries which continue to have the problem of unemployment and underemployment in spite of continuous policy emphasis and programmes to get rid of the problem it is to some point not able to jam up the space of unemployment and underdevelopment. This paper tries to find out the core cause of problems like unemployment in India. It tries to analyse the varying temperament of employment pre and post reform period and also the impact of globalisation on employment and development of India. The present paper explains the augmentation and structural conversion in employment in the extended and small period, through a particular spotlight on the phase from the time when economic liberalisation started. It gauges the employment challenge in its quantitative and qualitative magnitude and examines the forecast of generating productive employment of ample quantity and quality. It concludes with signs of a few broad measures of policy for faster growth of productive and decent employment in India.

Key Words: Employment, Development, Globalisation, Poverty, Challenges, Strategies & Policy Connotation Etc

Research Questions:

- ✓ What is the concept of employment and development in India?
- ✓ What is the changing nature of employment in India?
- ✓ How does the employment contributing towards Economic Development?
- ✓ What are the challenges of employment and development?
- ✓ What is the impact of globalization on employment and development?

Objectives of the Paper:

The proposed study aims to investigate into the impact of globalization on employment and development in India and the objective of the study are:

- ✓ To identify the concept of employment and development
- ✓ To analyze the process of globalization and its impact on India
- ✓ To examine the strategy of employment before the era of globalization
- ✓ To examine the strategy of employment post-globalization era
- ✓ To find out the major challenges of employment and development in India

Sources of the Study:

The present study is based on primary and secondary sources. It is primarily based on secondary data i.e. Annual Reports of the Ministry of Labor and Employment, Five Year Plans, Economic Surveys, books, journals, newspapers, research papers, essays etc and partially on quantitative and Histro analytical comparative methodology.

Introduction:

Growth has been above all since the post reform period of the 1990s. The person, who does not get work even for this duration, is known as unemployed. Unemployment turns out as a person who is unambiguously penetrating for employment is vulnerable to find work. Unemployment is over and over again used as a measure of the health of the economy. We can make out unemployment a solemn dilemma which is not always easy to spot. Accelerating growth and expanding employment opportunities are the goals of economic policy. To provide productive employment for the continuing increase in the labour force is an integral part of our objective of inclusive growth. In a broad sense, there is no conflict between the two objectives of growth and employment. Over time, the two go together. Higher growth leads to enhanced employment¹. Employment elasticity varies from sector to sector. Some sectors, by their very nature, are labour intensive. Also demand for labour depends on the relative prices of capital and labour. In a labour abundant economy, the price of labour is cheaper than that of capital, favouring labour intensive technologies wherever feasible. Thus any programme aimed at expanding employment opportunities must focus on three factors – growth, productivity of labour and relative price of labour and capital. The structural changes that occur in the process of growth have also a bearing on employment trends. India has come a long way in establishing and guaranteeing the rights of labour. We need to modify our labour laws as circumstances change without diluting the basic rights guaranteed to workers. Globalisation inexorably leads to an attack on workers' rights. Globalization affects the employment situation through trade liberalization, through encouragement of exports and imports and through increasing incentives for investment and innovation. It also encourages FDI which supplements domestic investment and leads to higher growth of the Economy. Globalisation would effect in momentous enhancement in labour concentrated exports in that manner promoting employment and income generation in developing countries². The paper is devoted to a discussion of the impact of globalisation on growth and employment, employment diversification, income inequality and on poverty reduction in India. The discussion starts with a brief review of the trends in growth and employment and changes in employment structure in India since the early 1970s in general, and since 1991, in particular. An effort is also made to intimately look at the issue of quality of new employment being generated through globalisation after 1991. The most important aims and objectives of liberalization and globalization are to pick up the quality of goods and services, to increase the employment opportunities, stick together in the competition at the international level, and recover the production capability at the domestic level. The collective and most urgent grievance of informal workers is instability of employment, and women workers who were conferred with about their grievances were no exception. Most of them had no formal employment prominence, and could be released for any grounds whatsoever, including asking for a rise in their below-minimum wages.

Concept of Development:

Development means “upgrading in country’s economic and social conditions “more specifically it refers to enhancement in a way of overseeing an area’s natural and human resources .In order to generate wealth and progress of people’s lives .The citizens are held to be principle actors in human scale expansion .With regard to the assortment of people’s as well as the self-sufficiency of the places in which they must proceed or renovates the nearby day object person to a subject in the human dimension development .The development of the assortment that we have experienced has mainly been a top down approach where there is a little leeway of well-liked contribution and decision making³.

Development is more than enhancement in people’s well being: it also describes the competence of the organization to provide the circumstances for those improvements in individual well being are a benchmark by which it is judged. This has imperative implications for development policy both for developing country’s themselves wishing to situate their economy and society onto a path of faster development and for outsiders who want to help that process .We are at an near the beginning at juncture of exploring those connotations⁴

Relation between Growth and Development:

Growth and development are from time to time used synonymously in economic discourse. Although the usage is sporadically acceptable it can baffle the two expressions can have different meanings, unspoken in general use and overt in what follows in scrupulous, economic growth means more productivity. Economic development implies more productivity but also different kinds of productivity than were previously produced as well as changes in the technical and institutional bargain by which output is produced and distributed .Growth may involve greater contribution leading to greater productivity. It may also a consequence from superior competence. Development goes ahead of this to take account of changes in the masterpiece of productivity and in the virtual sizes of contributions of the various inputs to the productive process.⁶

Concept of Employment:

Employment is an affiliation flanked by two parties, frequently based on a bond where work is paid for, where one party, which may be a firm, not-for-profit organization, or other entity is the employer and the employee⁷. Employment is like the equilibrium of economic competence and social justice and the crucial debate in this meadow of employment and its relations. By assembling the needs of the employer; generating profits to determine and uphold economic effectiveness; even as maintaining a sense of balance with the

employee and creating social equity that reimbursed the worker so that he/she can subsidize and enjoy healthy livelihood; proves to be a uninterrupted spinning subject in westernized nation⁸. Employment is a permissible notion that is essential for shaping the legal fortification, societal acknowledgment, and monetary safety linked up with diverse profile of work. As a permissible kind employment is exceedingly discriminating; if not paid work hysteric into the slender opening of employment it is nearly unfettered, In part, the complexity of defining the terms “employment” and “self-employment” arises from the piece of evidence that their definitions depend upon the context in which they are being used. Self-employment is assorted and a great deal of it is likely to be unstable in terms of pay, benefits, and security. But regardless of this societal authenticity, the idyllic of self-employment keep on influencing the legal standard of employment and consequently are at a standstill used to rationalize exclusive of self-employed workers as of labour protection and much societal reimbursement.⁹

Development Strategies in Indian Scenario:

In the direction of to draw attention to the foremost features of visualization of India’s development and the role of Government along with its planning strategy people have to emphasize the main attribute of that vision ,one have got to contemplate on a number of the majority essential goals ,the reinforcement of some of the most indispensable objectives and the emerging challenges .Our national goals are the manifestation of our combined aspirations as decoded into viable targets in the direction of the closing stages of the set goals target we would akin to distinguish ourselves nationwide completely free from the spring of poverty ,illiteracy and unemployment we would like to come out as a state in which all young human being come forward to and is guaranteed of a satisfying and gainful bustle slot in. We would like to see a social system and an economic environment in which there are plenty of choices and chock-full liberty of choices are made accessible to everyone for the fuller development of his/her human potentials .This is promising merely with a well-brought-up standard of living for all diversified probabilities of education, decent health services and a minimum of social security accessible to all. In order to get these essential human goals we all have to accomplish and uphold economic growth rate of at least 8 percent in the larger of the coming period. Our immediate challenge is to put down the obligatory foundation for this higher growth trail within the earlier few years of the coming time.¹⁰

The most important goal of India’s development approach has been to set up a socialistic society accompanied by economic growth self-reliance, social justice and alleviation of poverty. These objectives were to be achieved within a self-governing political structure using the apparatus of a assorted economy where both public and private sectors co-exist¹¹

A number of factors contributing to India’s provincial development are; -rest, changes in agriculture and the rural development that are key to India’s economic development, dynamic features, that fetch about foremost provincial changes as measurement of economic liberalization to embrace reorganization of spatial structures pertaining to industrialization and the configuration of new industrial regions, the succession of urbanization and development of major cities, and economic growth¹²

Contemporarily the planning responsibilities in India can be alienated into three categories; they are Agricultural and related development programmes, Development of social services and the lastly the Urban development¹³

The categorization follows generally the sectoral classification in the five year plans. Ever since Independence, the Government of India has initiated the developmental planning method and implemented them through the Five Year Plans. Up to now, even though Twelfth Five Year Plans have been implemented, still the problem of rural poverty, unemployment and regional imbalances has stayed behind largely unexplained. Even the fundamental infrastructural amenities are lost in largely and generally in the villages¹⁴

Performance of Employment and Development (Pre-Globalisation Era):

India later than the independence started economic development and the foremost objective of our five year plans was, to boost up the velocity of economic growth ,which would eventually facilitate us to increase the employment and reduce disparity in all spears .So ,for first Nine Five Year Plans ,the Annual Plans were intended and got implemented In all these plans ,huge investments was made in key sectors to amplify the peace of development and expected that the reimbursement of growth would stretch to all sections of the people .But five decades of planned development have not made any momentous upshot in dissemination the reimbursement to diverse sections of the community and the objective of planning in India was to rise the per capita income and to guarantee that the benefits are evenly disseminated between regions and the people. However after few decades of planning, the amount of development achieved is far-off from reasonable by the year 1990, more than 40 percent of the population was living below the poverty line. The economy was suffering with very low growth rate of high levels of unemployment, low levels of exports, high levels of imports and crisis in balance of payments. To resolve the exertions of low economic growth rate and balance of payment crisis government of India has initiated the policy reform measures like structural adjustments program, liberalisation and globalisation .These measures lead to market economy where market regulates the economy and role of state is reduced .These reforms are based on the belief that once macro-economic

stabilization is achieved, it will revise the structural characteristics of the economy and show the way to sustainable economic growth¹⁵

After Independence, the country embarked on an striving task of planned economic growth to budge the country out of the critical stagnation of the pre-independence era. The country had also to consider with the after effects of the Second World War and partition, in addition to consolidating the nation and building an administrative and political apparatus. As three complex tasks were being tackled, the country had to face famines and wars during the sixties and the seventies and early eighties¹⁶

By the 1980's, earlier than India's own early liberalisation programme really took off, India was already in extensive teething troubles on the employment frontage. Largely, but not at all, of the problems were observable to developments within India's own domestic economy, and unconnected to events outside it. In the organised industrial sector, nevertheless, the impact of both changes in the long term development approach and creeping liberalisation was obvious. As in India, employment growth rates, normally, fell below population and labour force growth rates by the start of the 1980s. In organised manufacturing, employment growth rates came down to very close to zero during the 1980s. Conversely, the jagged decline in employment prospects was, and still is above all a rural problem it is far serious in urban areas. As table 1 in rural areas the problem lies mainly in agriculture¹⁷.

Table 1: Growth of employment 1972-73 to 1987-88: Total, Rural and Urban

		Reference Period		
		1977-73 to 1977-78	1977-78 to 1983	1983 to 1987-88
1	Total	2.82	2.22	1.55
2	Rural	2.52	1.74	0.95
3	Urban	4.31	4.36	3.84

Source NSS Data Covering Usual Principal Status and Subsidiary Status:

And effect is that rural areas have not only been exporting their labour force to urban areas, they have also been exporting their unemployment. Given the much higher rates of growth of urban employment, it is not astonishing that rural unemployed or underemployed gravitated to the cities. These developments were associated with the increasing casualisation of the workforce, in rural areas in particular, during the 1970s and 1980s. While the casualisation phenomenon is not confined to rural areas.

Expansion of employment at national level has been one of the most vital goals of Indian Plans since 1951. Significantly Plans objective was followed for generation of new employment opening as also the diminution of unemployment. Employment targets in early Plans largely aimed at eliminating obviously apparent unemployment. The objective of the First Plan was to get full employment but later Plans had to choose less ambitious and more realistic targets. As a matter of fact in the premature phase of planning, a noteworthy shift of investment towards heavy industry and organised manufacturing was made as a major strategy was most obviously reflected in the Second Plan was less than 5%. In view of the success of earlier Plans in this regard the latter Plans may be adjudged realistic from the standpoint of generating employment opportunities. For occurrence, the Sixth Plan had aimed at modest target (i.e., creating employment for only the new entrants to the labour force. This Plan succeeded in achieving targets by and large keeping long term employment objective in view, the uppermost investment precedence should go to areas such as power generation and manufacturing though the immediate result for increasing employment opportunities, construction and service sectors may preferably be considered in formulating Plan Policy. However, for maximising employment in the country in the instantaneous future, a comparatively sooner growth of agriculture based manufacturing industries should be achieved with a very strong association between agriculture and manufacturing units over the short-run. The food industry though hitting no remarkable short-run promise for the sake of direct employment opportunities, it is really very attractive in its inter-linkage role and prevalence in the perspective of Indian economy. Adjacent to the surroundings of the aforesaid analysis, the potentiality of employment generation for 40 million people during the Seventh Plan period (1985-1990), there will be 39 million new entrants in the working labour class. Almost all the Five Year Plans have given higher priority to balanced regional development and removal of regional disparities in income. But quite contrary to the goal, during the different Plan periods per capita inter-regional income disparities have been on increase considerably despite the fact that that transfer of resources from the Central Government was oriented more and more in favour of the poor States¹⁸. The time from 1969 to 1973 witnessed a passionate radicalization of economic policy through huge range nationalization of banking and industry and additional retrenchment of restrictions on the private sector in the name of shortening monopolies¹⁹

During the first three decades of economic planning, the GDP growth rate was as near to the ground as 3.5 percent per annum. In this period, employment augmented at a level-headed rate of 2 % per annum. Conversely, thereafter, while the GDP growth rate picked up considerably, employment growth rate recorded a sharp drop. Indeed, while employment growth was as high as 2.82 percent per annum over the five year period 1972-73 to 1977-78 it fell to only 1.02 percent per annum over the five year period 1993-94 to 1999-2000²⁰

Unemployment was renowned as the hitch from the very starting of the planning process in India. Consequently employment generation was acknowledged as goal of development planning. However a quicker growth with unique stress on employment –concentrated sectors like the small scale industry was considered adequate to generate employment of the order required to take care of the problem²¹

Performance of Employment and Development in (Post Globalisation Era):

Employment has a very imperative role to play in pleasing to the eye of human capabilities. It not only ensures economic protection, but also promotes general contribution in society and the economy. Employment is necessary for promoting better health and education not only for those who are employed, but also for those who are dependent relative on them. In adding up, it makes available a sense of majesty to the individual. One of the biggest confront facing the country nowadays is to efficiently and profitably make use of its growing labour force, which is obligatory for attaining the objective of inclusive growth. Subsequent to a turn down in the annual growth rate of employment from 2.6 % amid 1983-84 and 1993-94 to 1.25 percent between 1993-94 and 1999-2000, it grew all over again at 2.6 percent between 1999-2000 and 2004-05. Nevertheless since the annual growth rate of labour force between 1999-2000 and 2004-05 was higher than the annual growth rate of workforce, there was an increase in the unemployment rate. The unemployment rate (current daily status) increased from 7.3 percent in 1999-2000 to 8.3 percent in 2004-05. According to the usual principal status; the unemployment rate in 2004-05 was 5.3 percent. The growth rate of employment has clearly not been commensurate with GDP growth. There was hardly any increase in the annual rate of employment growth during the period 1999-2000 to 2007-08 (a period which experienced acceleration in GDP growth) as compared to 1993-04 to 1999-2000. Growth rate of employment in urban areas increased from 2.3 percent during the period 1993-94 to 1999-2000 to only 2.6 percent during the period 1999-2000 to 2007-08. In rural India, the annual growth rate of employment was only 1.27 percent during the period 1999-2000 to 2007-08 as compared to 0.66 percent during the period 1993-94 to 1999-2000. The fact that there has not been any significant growth in employment despite considerable acceleration in GDP growth 'points to a significant fall in the elasticity of employment with respect to output'²²

The need to ensure sufficient growth in employment opportunities to generate productive employment for the rolling increase in the labour force is extensively regarded as one of the most important tasks facing the country. There is prevalent concern that the hastening in GDP growth in the post-reforms period has not been gone together by a commensurate development in employment. Public sector employment is likely to fall as the public sector withdraws from many areas. There are uncertainties that the progression of internal liberalization and globalisation are creating a situation, which is not conducive to expanding employment in the overloaded labour in order to stay on spirited and new-fangled technology, which is vital to ensure competitiveness, is usually more robotic and consequently not job creating. The net consequence of these forces, it is dreadful, and could be a very slow expansion in employment opening in the organised sector, with a rise in unemployment rates and mounting annoyance among youth²³. Rural employment in the Indian economy had grown-up at a vigorous rate throughout the period 1999-2000 to 2004-05. The usual principal and subsidiary status (UPSS) employment growth rate between 1999-2000 and 2004-05 to be 2.34%²⁴ and the usual principal status (UPS) based rural employment growth rates to be 2.67%. This rise in employment growth is being lauded since it occurred after a period of jobless growth, all through 1993-94 to 1999-2000. However, the intriguing fact remains that such an impressive employment growth occurred during the phase of an almost complete stagnation of output growth in the agricultural sector, the mainstay of rural economy²⁵

India's contribution to global growth in PPP terms augmented from an average of 8.3 per cent during the period 2001 to 2007 to 14.4 per cent in 2014. During the 1990s, the US's contribution to the global GDP growth in PPP terms was, on an average, around 16 percentage points higher than India's. The picture changed dramatically in 2013 and 2014 when India's contribution was higher than that of the US by 2.2 and 2.7 percentage points respectively. During 1991-2014, low growth in Japan (0.9 per cent annually) resulted in its low contribution (1.5 per cent) to global growth. India and China constitute 42.5 per cent and 53.2 per cent respectively of the total PPP measure of the lower-middle income countries and upper-middle income countries; and hence those country groups largely reflect India's and China's patterns. The global economy—in particular the global growth powerhouse, China—is rebalancing, leading to an increasing role for India. Later than the commencement of the numerous crises in diverse parts of the world, India's involvement has become much more valuable to the global economy. India's share in world GDP has increased from an average of 4.8 per cent during 2001-07 to 6.1 per cent during 2008-13 and further to an average of 7.0 per cent during 2014 to 2015 in current PPP terms (IMF). India's elasticity and existing levels of sensibly strong growth should, thus, be long-awaited in the light of its increasing involvement to global growth²⁶

Impact of Globalisation on Employment in India:

Despite the fact that employment situation in the informal sector have not distorted drastically - and, certainly, could barely have got not as good as than they were to begin with - the formal sector, which was characterised by elevated levels of job safety, union density and collective bargaining up to the 1970s, suffered a disastrous corrosion of job safety from the 1980s onwards. Textile mills, for example, went through a eye-

catching turn down in employment. It is estimated that the Bombay textile strike of 1982-83 was followed by the loss of roughly 75,000 jobs due to closures and downsizing, excluding jobs where older workers were replaced by new recruits²⁷ By the closing stages of the 1990s, this number estimated to have climbed to 100,000 jobs. In Ahmadabad, another textile centre, the turn down started in 1982, with the closure of 50 private mills and 20 government-owned mills and the loss of almost 100,000 jobs over the next fifteen years, the majority in the 1980s²⁸

In this day and age Globalization is being talked everywhere by everyone. Government officials and different national and international organizations are studying the impact of Globalization on various aspects in India including its impact on employment. The impact of Globalization on employment in India pervades far-off and extensive as the reforms integrated ever since 1991-92 led to the access of numerous worldwide employers in India and also served to open up various employment avenues. It should be kept in mind that the process of economic reforms was in full swing with the one and only aim of getting better living conditions of the people of the country. It was the stand for and not the end in itself. Reforms were started not for diminishing the employment avenues. The impact of globalization and employment in India is positive as the globalization process has led to the increase of employment avenues Globalization has led the technological advancement in a gigantic way. The world is experiencing a prototype of technological move forwards and that has escort in a period of jobless growth. It is usual and up to a tip advantageous for growth in unemployment to lag behind growth in output. Change has definitely brought a large shift in the composition of demand for labour. But new technology has also created plenty of jobs and we cannot keep away from this fact but the problem of unemployment arises when an adequate response by way of a change in the composition of labour supply is offered either by lack of admittance to training and education or by an endeavour to protect the employment of low demand categories of labour by unsuitable variety of intrusion. To pull off the objective of full employment in the years to come, policies have to encourage those sectors in which employment opportunities are high must be adopt like automobile, agriculture and small scale industries²⁹.

Challenges of Employment in India:

Increase in Labour Force:

From the time when independence achieved, an occupant of India has registered an exceptional growth, followed by a usual development in labour force. Women education has malformed their outlook towards employment. However, our economy has devastating to act in response to these changes and all this has caused a constant increase in unemployed accumulation. Between 2000 and 2010, 64 million jobs approximately were generated in India³⁰

Inadequate Planning Strategy:

Unemployment is a solemn crisis which indicates a state of affairs where the overall number of employment is much less than the total number of employment seekers in the country. It is a type of state of affairs where the unemployed people do not come across any significant or profitable job regardless of having eagerness and capability to work.³¹

Increase in Population:

Indian economy is underdeveloped and role of economic growth is very slow. This slow growth fails to endow with enough employment opportunities to the increasing population. Continuous increases in population have been a immense problem in India it is one of the most important causes of unemployment Population control .The augmentation of population should be checked in order to get rid of unemployment, problem. Family planning programme should be put into practice widely and successfully³²

Agriculture is a Seasonal Occupation:

Agriculture is undersized in India which provides seasonal employment. Huge part of population is dependent relative on agriculture. However agriculture being seasonal provides work for a few months as a result this gives rise to unemployment. An important cause liable for slow growth of employment opportunities is the neglect of agriculture for generating employment opportunities³³.

Low Growth of Industrialisation:

The velocity of industrial growth is sluggish. Despite the fact that emphasis is laid on industrialisation nevertheless the avenues of employment generated by industrialisation are very a small number of Lack of full employment in industries: In the industrial sector, at hand is there is same lack of full employment. There are not a lot of mills and factories and the number of men employed in them is not large. Even the mills and factories that we have do not work to their highest capability either for want for of requisite machinery or for lack of satisfactory supply of materials³⁴.

Focus on Small Establishments:

In India, about 95 per cent of establishments employ less than 20 workers and 60 per cent of the workers serve in such establishments. Therefore, the labour policies and programmes must focus on the requirement of small establishments³⁵.

Under Employment:

Insufficient availability of means of invention is the main cause of under employment. People do not get employment for the whole year due to shortage of electricity, coal and raw materials.

Inequitable Distribution of Land:

Another cause of unemployment existing in the developing countries like India is unbalanced sharing of land so that many agricultural households have not sufficient access to land which is an important asset for agricultural production and employment. Sub-division of land holdings under the pressure of rapid population growth from the time many persons who were self-employed in agriculture have become landless agricultural labourers who suffer from sensitive unemployment and underemployment³⁶

Defective Education System:

Educated youth is the mainstay of a nation's hope. India is a newly-born independence. We have to put up her up from very graze. It is the educated young men and women, on whose shoulder lays the great responsibility of making India an ideally socialist state. Our youth on their own part, must make it a standard that they should not scuttle behind the supposedly glimmer of urban life, rather they should inhabit in villages, in that way contributing their proportion of services in the development of our villages. University education must be lay under assured limitations. Merely those students may perhaps be authorized to hold on a post-graduate college, who have secured as a minimum a high second division in their basic examinations³⁷. This would set a conclusion to the process of producing mass graduates, which have intensified the dilemma of unemployment. More technical, medical and agricultural colleges have to be established larger than the country and Government aid and scholarships have to be granted to the commendable student. The unemployment problem, particularly among the educated youth of India, should be given a solemn deliberation to by the government, as the youth of these days is to be the stake of the country's hope but the intensifying generation is discouraged and degenerated; if its strength of mind and fervours are chilled under the impact of unemployment, our country will not be capable to formulate any considerable advance in future³⁸.

Voluntary Unemployment:

Voluntary unemployment is a situation when a person is unemployed not due to unavailability of jobs in the economy, but because of not being able to find employment of his/her own choice. People reject employment opportunities if they do not receive desired wages or if they are not offered the kind of work they wish to do i.e. unemployed of their own will³⁹. The unemployment across the country, where people choose not to work below a certain income level after 'investing' in education. If a sufficient number of jobs are not created, it can lead to a great deal of resentment, because of aspirations⁴⁰. Job creation in India is not expected to pick up pace in 2017 and 2018 as unemployment rises slightly, representing a near stagnation in percentage terms. Unemployment in India is projected to increase from 17.7 million last year to 17.8 million in 2017 and 18 million next year. In percentage terms, unemployment rate will remain at 3.4 per cent in 2017-18⁴¹

Conclusion:

Unless unemployment crisis is solved, the development point of view of India cannot be vivid. There will be no concord and affluence in the country if jobless people do not get a proper passage and extra notice should be set otherwise this problem can create jobless youths go to off beam track. Unemployment and poverty goes alongside. The problem of unemployment gives mount to the problem of poverty and our Youthful people after a long time of unemployment come across the wrong way to make money. To get rid from the unemployment strain, they accept alcohol or drugs out of continuous failure of getting employment sometimes unemployed youths accepts suicide as the last option of their life lesser economic growth Increase rate in Crimes. As the employed youth don't have anything to do they start doing robbery, murder etc. Health issues i.e. it affects mentally as well as physically and the very first solution for the unemployment is to control the rising population of our country. Government should stimulate people to have small families Our Indian government has started plans to control the population but still the population is rising. The quality of Indian education should be improved. The current education system is not up to the level to fulfil the needs of students getting a degree for name sake should not be the priority our education system should look over the solution to provide employable education where people don't feel like to go outside India and through this effort situation like brain drain can be decrease. There is still much more to think about.

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